

MULTIPLE FIBER BREAKAGE BEHAVIOR ON SINGLE YARN FRAGMENTATION TEST OF NATURAL FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

It is known that a single yarn is formed by spinning natural short fibers and a twist yarn consists of some single fibers in order to achieve high stiffness and strength of natural fiber composites. Generally, it is found that the amount of twist obtained by the spinning process, called twist per inch (TPI), plays an important role in yarn properties because the twist is essential to hold the fibers together. In fact, twisted yarns are normally used for increasing the lateral cohesion of the fibers and also for ease of handling. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of TPI of natural fiber yarns on multiple fiber breakages and stress recovery behavior for natural fiber composites. The single yarn composites with three kinds of TPI from 3.5 to 9.5 were prepared. These yarns consisted of three single natural fibers. The fragmentation tests using these yarn composites under a polarization microscope were carried out. The multiple fiber breakages were experimentally confirmed, but the effect of TPI on the stress recovery length was not cleared quantitatively. It was considered that the factors of these unwilling results were the twist angle, project and surface areas of fibers because the stress recovery length depends on the fiber project, surface area and axial stress. In order to investigate the stress concentration of sound fibers and the stress recovery of broken fiber, some finite element analyses were conducted. From the analyses, it was found that the effect of TPI on the stress recovery behavior and the stress concentration of sound fibers were cleared. Furthermore, the load shearing behaviors between sound fibers were different because the twist angle effects on the fiber axial direction change.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, natural fiber reinforced composites are expected as structural materials, and already applied to industrial products such as car interior parts and electrical products [1]. Natural fiber made from plants mainly consists of cellulose, which has a high elastic modulus of 138GPa in its crystal part [2]. Then it is expected that the natural fiber will widely be substituted for conventional glass fibers. The research and development of materials using the biomass sources provide the opportunity for a sustainable society.

It is known that a single yarn is formed by spinning natural short fibers and a twist yarn consists of some single yarns in order to achieve high stiffness and strength of natural fiber composites. Generally, it is found that the amount of twist obtained by the spinning process, called twist per inch (TPI), plays an important role in yarn properties because the twist is essential to hold the fibers together [3]. In fact, twisted yarns are normally used for increasing the lateral cohesion of the fibers and also for ease of handling. By twisting yarns, possible micro damages within the yarn can be localized, leading to possible increase in the failure strength of the yarn [4].

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of TPI of natural fiber yarns on multiple fiber breakages and stress recovery length for natural fiber composites. The single yarn composites with various TPI were prepared. The fragmentation tests using these yarn composites under a polarization microscope were carried out. Moreover, in order to investigate the stress concentration of sound

fibers and the stress recovery of broken fiber, some finite element analyses for single yarn composites under tensile loading were conducted.

2 MATERIALS, SPECIMENS AND IN-SITU OBSERVATIONS

2.1 Materials and specimens

The natural fiber reinforcement used in this study was a ramie single yarn (No.16, supplied by TOSCO, CO., Ltd). Some filaments were pulled out from the yarn. Three filaments twisted yarns were manually produced from these filaments. The numbers of twists (TPI; Twist per inch) prepared were 3.5, 6.5 and 9.5 /inch. The bio-based thermosetting resin, acrylated epoxidized soybean oil (AESO, Ebecryl 860 produced by Daicel-allnex Co., Ltd) was used as matrix for single yarn composites. This composite is then fully bio-based composites. The hardeners for resin were a t-butyl peroxybenzoate produced by Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd. The viscosity of AESO resin is 26.5 Pa s at 25 °C. The viscosity of resin decreased to add the thinner. Styrene monomer produced by Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd. was used as thinner. The ratio between AESO, hardener and thinner was 100 : 1.5 : 15, at that time, the viscosity of mixed resin was approximately 2.0 Pa s. The mold jig made from a Teflon plate was shown in Figure 1-(a). The both edges of single yarn were fixed by tape, and a weight of 0.2g was applied to one edge in order to apply the constant tension for single yarn. The mold jig with single yarn having tension was sandwiched in glass plates after the resin input. The resin was cured at 100 °C for 2 hours, then a post-cured at 120 °C for 2 hours. The materials trimmed to the dimension of specimen, were buffed to mirror surface and the resin plate tabs were glued to the specimens as shown in Figure 1-(b).

(a) Mold jig to apply the constant tension

(b) Shape of the specimen

Figure 1: Specimen preparation for single yarn composites

2.2 In-situ observation system

The fragmentation tests using above yarn composites under a polarization microscope were carried out as shown in Figure 2. Tensile tests were conducted at room temperature and the cross-head speed was 0.5 mm/min.

(a) Overall view

(b) Tensile loading system

Figure 2: In-situ observation system

3 FRAGMENTATION TEST RESULTS

Figure 3 shows the polarization photographs for some fiber breakages at strain level before final failure of single yarn composites. The multiple fiber breakages due to stress recovery were confirmed. In the vicinity of the fiber break, a small matrix crack occurred without fiber pull-out. From this result, it was found that the interfacial adhesion between natural fibers and AESO resin was enough. Figure 4 depicts the representative results for the relation between the fiber breakage density and applied strain. The stress recovery length L_c for each TPI was estimated using equation 1,

$$L_c = \frac{4 L_0}{3 n} \quad (1)$$

where, L_0 is the gauge length and n is the saturated number of fiber breakages. The obtained stress recovery lengths for TPI 3.5, 6.5 and 9.5 were 1.60, 2.22 and 2.11mm, respectively. It was found that the effect of TPI on the stress recovery length was not cleared quantitatively. It was considered that the factors of these unwilling results were the twist angle, project and surface areas of fibers because the stress recovery length depends on the fiber projected, surface area and axial stress. In the case of low TPI, the stress recovery length decreases as increase of fiber axial stress, since the fiber was aligned along to a yarn axial direction due to the reduction of twist angle. On the other hands, in the case of high TPI, the fiber axial stress decreases since the fiber projected area along the yarn axial direction and the surface area increase due to the increase of twist angle. The stress recovery length depends on the interaction between these mechanisms.

(a) TPI3.5 specimen at strain of 4.0 %
(b) TPI6.5 specimen at strain of 3.0 %
(c) TPI9.5 specimen at strain of 4.0 %
Figure 3: Multiple fiber breakages using polarization observation

Figure 4: Relation between the fiber breakages density and applied strain

4 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

4.1 FE model

In this section, finite element (FE) analyses were conducted in order to investigate the stress concentration of sound fibers near broken fiber and the stress recovery of the fiber. Four kinds of FE models consist of TPI 3.5, 6.5, 9.5 yarns and straight fibers were prepared in this study. FE models for single yarn composites included TPI 9.5 yarn were shown in figure 5. Figure 5-(b) shows the TPI 9.5 yarn in the composites with sixth part of entire length for round yarn. 10 and 4 nodes on tetrahedral solid elements were used for fibers and matrix, respectively. In the case of TPI 9.5, the number of elements for fibers and matrix are 30494. These elements were assumed to be linear elastic isotropic body. Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio for fiber and matrix were 24.5 GPa, 0.62 GPa, 0.33 and 0.33, respectively. For the boundary conditions, on one hand the circle face was bound along the z direction and the displacement corresponding to 2% strain was applied on the other hands along the z direction. Moreover, to model a fiber break a part of cross-section of fiber near binding face of one fiber was unconsolidated.

Figure 5: Finite element models

4.2 Analytical results

Figure 6 shows the stress contour of σ_{zz} distributions for 3 fibers in the straight fiber model, TPI 3.5, 6.5 and 9.5 models. Near broken fiber the stress concentration occurred for the sound fibers. Figure 7 depicts the stress recovery behavior of broken fiber and stress concentration of sound fibers along z direction. The fiber denominations in figure 7 were referred in figure 8. For the straight fibers model, it was found that the fiber stress of broken fiber didn't recover until far field stress. The stress recovery ratio to far field stress was 0.48. The traditional hexagonal fiber array model [5] was additionally conducted in order to confirm the effect of fiber array on the stress recovery behaviors. From this calculation, the stress recovery of broken fiber was enough until the far field stress and the stress concentration factor of sound fibers near broken fiber was 1.097. The stress concentration factor for hexagonal fiber array model was 1.104 [5]. In fact only two sound fibers near broken fiber was responsible for the inadequate stress recovery of broken fiber in present model. It was also denoted that the broken fiber in yarn using 3 fibers couldn't recover completely in stress. For the yarn models, it was found that the stress distributions of sound fibers were different although the stress concentrations of these fibers near broken fiber were almost equivalent. The increase in the difference with increasing TPI was cleared in figure 7.

Figure 6: Stress contour of σ_{zz} for fibers

Figure 7: Stress recovery of broken fiber and stress concentration of sound fibers along z direction (yarn axial direction)

Figure 8: Fiber array and node denominations

In order to examine the causes of difference between fiber 2 and 3 in σ_{zz} distributions, the τ_{rz} distributions of sound fibers at the interface were investigated. Here, the stress components in the Cartesian coordinate system were transformed to the components in the polar coordinates system at the local coordinate system which located in the center of fiber as the coordinate basis. Figure 9 shows τ_{rz} distributions for sound fibers in the straight fiber model along z direction. The positions from a to f were also defined as shown in figure 8. It was found that the stress at the position d of fiber 2 and the position c of fiber 3 indicated the highest values due to the stress concentrations. Both of these stress levels were almost same.

Figure 9: τ_{rz} distributions of sound fibers for 3 straight fibers model

τ_{rz} distributions for sound fibers in the TPI 9.5 model along z direction was shown in figure 10. The high stress concentrations occurred at the position from a to c of sound fiber 3, although no stress concentration occurred for sound fiber 2. The insensibility of fiber 2 causes the difference in stress distributions between fiber 2 and 3 as shown in figure 7. It was suggested that the spiral process of stress direction existed due to the twist structures.

Figure 10: τ_{rz} distributions of sound fibers for TPI 9.5 model

5 CONCLUSIONS

In order to investigate the effect of TPI of natural fiber yarns on multiple fiber breakages and stress recovery length for natural fiber composites, the fragmentation tests using single yarn composites with various TPI under a polarization microscope were carried out. Then, the multiple fiber breakages due to stress recovery were experimentally confirmed. Moreover, in order to investigate the stress concentration of sound fibers and the stress recovery of broken fiber, some finite element analyses for single yarn composites under tensile loading were conducted. In the case of straight fiber model, it was found that the broken fiber in yarn using 3 fibers couldn't recover completely in stress. On the other hands, for the yarn models, it was found that the stress distributions of sound fibers were different although the stress concentrations of these fibers near broken fiber were almost equivalent. The increase in the difference with increasing TPI was cleared. From the calculation of shear stress for sound fibers, it was suggested that the spiral process of stress direction existed due to the twist structures.

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